

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INCREASING THE ROLE OF INNOVATIONS IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE NON-OIL SECTOR

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Abstract

The article explains the development of the non-oil sector in modern times, export growth, favorable business environment, investment attraction, continuous improvement of infrastructure, expansion of integration relations. The role of innovations in increasing the export potential of the non-oil sector. sources of funding in the field of innovation, world experience, etc. investigated.

Keywords: national business, innovation potential, innovation economy, innovative development, innovation strategy.

Content of the case

The socio-economic policy pursued by President Ilham Aliyev and the diversification of the economy, which is one of the main directions of this policy, play an exceptional role in ensuring the sustainable development of Azerbaijan. President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev states that "The main goal of the new economic development program is to develop the non-oil sector in our country, diversify the economy and support the private sector."

One of the main goals of the Strategic Road Map, approved by the Presidential Decree dated December 6, 2016, is to ensure the development of the non-oil sector. As a result of multifaceted and fundamental reforms, the non-oil sector is developing in Azerbaijan, our export opportunities are expanding, and dependence on imports is decreasing. At the heart of all these successes is the unity of people and power and the principle of mutual trust.

The Strategic Roadmap for the National Economic Perspective covers three periods - short-term, medium-term and long-term - 2020, 2025 and 2025.

Successful implementation of strategic roadmaps under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev contributes to macroeconomic stability, growth of the non-oil sector and exports, improvement of trade and fiscal balance, favorable business environment, investment attraction, sustainable infrastructure improvement, social welfare and integration of our country [1].

At present, it is planned to strengthen Azerbaijan's integration into the world economy and join the group of high-income countries.

Ensuring the development of the non-oil sector in order to increase the efficiency of the economy and increase competitiveness in our country is one of the main priorities of the national economy. To this end, as a result of successful economic policies pursued in the country, along with the achievement of economic diversification, the share of the non-oil sector in Gross Domestic Product has increased significantly. [2]

Economy Minister Mikayil Jabbarov said on Twitter that the export potential of the non-oil sector has been restored with confidence and

speed. He noted that in January-June this year, non-oil exports increased by 27.1% compared to the first half of last year and exceeded \$ 1.16 billion in monetary terms. At the same time, exports of non-oil products increased by 40.1% and its share in total non-oil exports exceeded 50%. In general, the total export volume for 6 months increased by 14.8% year on year. Further, the growth of exports has a positive impact on financial stability, creating new jobs and ensuring the stability of our foreign exchange reserves. Ensuring the competitiveness of development plays an exceptional role.

It is very important for our republic that the economic development of enterprises in accordance with the requirements of a market economy is formed on the basis of the principle of competitiveness. In the Global Competitiveness Index, Azerbaijan ranked 64th in 2006, behind Russia (62nd) and Kazakhstan (56th). As a result of economic development in the country over the past 10 years, according to the "Global Competitiveness Index 2013-2014", Azerbaijan ranked 39th in terms of competitiveness, ahead of countries such as Russia and Kazakhstan, and 1st in the CIS. It is ranked 51st in terms of innovation and 35th in terms of innovation potential. Azerbaijan ranks 71st in terms of real GDP per capita. These indicators show the development of the country's economy at the macro and micro levels, increasing its competitiveness. [3].

The strengthening of the modern process of globalization and its impact on national economies has made it necessary to make fundamental changes in scientific and practical views that serve to ensure the competitiveness of enterprises.

In the context of modern globalization and increasing openness of Azerbaijani markets to foreign business, the issue of increasing the competitiveness of the economy has become even more urgent.

At present, one of the most important directions of the state's economic policy in Azerbaijan is to increase the competitiveness and ensure the innovative development of existing enterprises in the country.

It should be noted that business structures in our country - newly created and modernized enterprises -

do not work to create new products, new technologies, but to produce competitive products that exist in the market. These companies already prefer to buy and apply technologies used in foreign markets, or to cooperate with foreign companies. One or two enterprises are engaged in the production of any specific product in the country at the same time, and the application of customs and tax duties on imports of these products, transport costs, artificial barriers in the import process allow producers to gain a certain competitive advantage. [4]

Research shows that most innovations implemented by enterprises are temporary. There are a limited number of innovations. This shows that the competition in the commodity markets is weak and many enterprises of the republic have a monopoly position.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan had a strong oil engineering industry until the 1990s. Due to the transition to a market economy from the first years of the transition period, the economic ties of the enterprises of this industry were broken, and as a result of the loss of traditional markets for their products, the industry fell into decline. In addition to losing supply and sales markets, oil companies have lost the opportunity to apply new equipment and technology, modernize existing production facilities, and thus produce quality products that meet international standards due to financial difficulties.

At present, mastering the production of products that meet the requirements of local and foreign markets, the application of investment policy, innovation strategies, modern management systems, marketing strategies, information and communication technologies is one of the important issues.

Production of competitive products in modern conditions is achieved, first of all, by achieving high profits by saving costs as a result of the application of innovation in the enterprise. To this end, any entrepreneur is interested in attracting innovation to the enterprise. The innovative form of entrepreneurship manifests itself in two directions: technological and product innovation. Technological innovation involves the further improvement of an existing product by applying innovation to the enterprise. Such entrepreneurship is based on the development of material and technical base. Product innovation involves the production of new products as consumer demand changes. In short, innovative entrepreneurship refers to economic entities that produce high quality products with advanced techniques and modern technological methods. Studies show that the winners in the world economy are the countries that have an effective innovation system, as well as the development of infrastructure that allows them to produce advanced products. The development of innovation-based entrepreneurship in our country is considered a key factor in economic diversification. Innovative innovations are usually made by large companies. This is due to the fact that this area requires large financial resources. However, small firms were able to bring this innovation to the enterprise faster, because these small firms are more flexible in adapting to changing needs.

According to the facts, the share of innovative products in the GDP of our country is about 5%, but in the developed countries of the world it is 8-9 times higher (40% -60%). According to research, the development of innovation in the country depends primarily on the development of human capital, ie, first of all, its level of education, knowledge and skills. From this point of view, the state program on "Education of youth abroad" for 2007-2015 has been developed for the development of human resources in our country. In many parts of the world, the private sector spends more on research (65% in the EU, 71% in Japan and 75% in the United States). However, this figure is low in our country (5%). Proper implementation of innovation activities of the enterprise depends, first of all, on the correct determination of the economic efficiency of innovation projects in the enterprise in advance and the choice of methods of implementation. The formation of innovative entrepreneurship, in turn, leads to the emergence of innovative employment. This is due to the fact that the workforce does not meet the requirements of high-tech production. Thus, the development of human potential is the basis for the formation of innovative employment.

Research shows that the socio-economic progress of any country depends on the development of science, human capital and innovation. The formation of an innovative national business determines the direction of the effective realization of the national economic power and interests of the country. For this purpose, formation of the country's technical and economic competitiveness for the implementation of the tasks envisaged in the socio-economic development strategy of the republic; improving the quality and competitiveness of national products; It is very important to increase state support for the innovative development of industries with comparative advantages. In addition, ensuring the access of innovative products to international markets; Encouraging the development of innovative industries in the regions by the state, the application of a number of concessions in the field of taxation and customs can be very effective. [5]

The results of reforms in the country show that new knowledge, technologies and their effective application to socio-economic development determine the country's place in the world community and ensuring national security. In this regard, given the limited resources of innovation, all economic systems must adhere to the norms of efficient use of their use. [6]

To achieve this goal, innovative technologies that meet modern requirements must be created in the country and their effective use must be ensured. Research shows that China, the United States, Germany, Italy, Japan, the Republic of South Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan and other countries are currently leading in the production and introduction of modern innovative technologies on the world market. Providing a favorable business environment, Azerbaijan ranked 63rd out of 189 countries in the 2016 World Bank's R Business report. At the same time, Azerbaijan ranks 40th among the world's

countries on 5 out of 10 indicators reflected in the World Bank. At the same time, in order to stimulate private sector investment in the non-oil economy, it is proposed to further improve the favorable business environment and strengthen its institutional framework.

It should be noted that the policy of import substitution and expansion of export potential in our country should be taken into account in the customs policy of our country. Thus, the experience of other countries shows that financial and credit mechanisms should be widely used to ensure the rapid development of the non-oil sector during import substitution and expansion of export potential. In addition, additional investment should be attracted in this area, tax rates should be reduced and customs tariffs regulatory tools must be used effectively.

Result

In the future, in accordance with the requirements of Azerbaijan's economic development strategy, the development of innovative national business in all sectors of the economy must be provided in a proportional manner. The development of innovative national business in the country should serve the realization of national economic interests. As progressive progress has been made in the socio-economic development of Azerbaijan, important steps have been taken in the export of innovative products in a number of areas. These include the products of the country's non-oil sector, the petrochemical industry, construction, cotton, tobacco and other products. However, in the development of innovative national business, it is expedient to pay more attention to the development of import-substituting products. Such products include machinery, machine tools and equipment for the processing and oil industries, cost-effective replacement resources, etc. can be attributed. In particular, in the development of the non-oil sector and the diversification of the economy, more investment is planned in the production of innovative products. Opportunities for foreign and domestic investment as a strong source of funding should be used effectively in the implementation of innovative measures in the non-oil sector in our country. [7]

To this end, the rate of return on investment must be taken into account in order to increase innovation assets. In order to increase innovation activity in the country, we consider it expedient to give priority to the implementation of the following measures:

1. Foreign and domestic investment in the development of the non-oil sector should be encouraged.

2. A favorable competitive and business environment must be created for the activities of innovative firms and companies.

3. The volume of investments in the replacement of physically and morally worn-out fixed assets in the republic should be increased.

4. Investments in the application of innovative technologies in existing industries should be encouraged.

5. Opportunities to limit the flow of capital from the republic to foreign countries and direct it to innovation-oriented areas should be expanded.

6. Attention should be paid to the development of innovation-oriented priority areas in the country, taking into account comparative advantages.

7. In order to ensure the active participation of our country in the regional integration blocs, the production of innovation-oriented products in the international market should be stimulated.

The application of all these measures will lead to the rapid development of the non-oil sector in our country and the improvement of the material well-being of the population.

References

1. "Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the Strategic Road Map for the National Economic Prospects of the Republic of Azerbaijan. December 6, 2016.

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the State Program of Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2014-2018. February 27, 2014 11.

3. Azerbaijan's foreign economic relations: achievements and prospects. Institute of Economics of ANAS. Baku: "Europe" publishing house, 2015.

4. A.Musayev. Innovation economy and tax incentives.

5. Z.M.Najafov. Basics of national innovation systems. Baku: "Science", 2006.

6. A.D.Hüseynova. Analysis of innovation potential in Azerbaijan. Baku: "Science and education", 2013.

7. ZA Shakaraliyeva Improving the regulation of the export potential of the non-oil sector. News magazine of the ENECO-Center for Energy Economy Baku №1,2022, p. 13-14